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Analysis of English language learning in grade 5 SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency

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Abstract

This study aims to describe (1) What are forms of literacy skills in English language learning?, (2) What is the level of difficulty of knowledge of fifth grade students in literacy during English learning at SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency. The subject of this study consisted of the principal, English teachers and fifth grade students. The type of this research is descriptive qualitative. The data collected were documents from the English teacher. English teacher as well as the participial. Data sources are divided into two, namely primary data sources in the form of the results of data collection using observation, interviews questionnaires while secondary data sources school profile, lesson schedule, student list, and list of educators. Data validity is carried out by means of data triangulation in the process consists of three interrelated stages, namely data reduction, data presentation and conclusion making. The results of the study revealed that the forms namely listening, speaking, writing, and reading. The level difficulty in writing seen from the analysis of interview data, questionnaires in and observation.

Keywords : *Analysis, Learning, English*

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INTRODUCTION

English in Indonesia according to Wijaya, Iriany Kesuma (2015:122) is generally taught as a foreign language, the term foreign language in the field of language teaching is different from second language. With the second language, Iriani Kesuma Wijaya argues that the foreign language it self is language that is not used as a means of communication in a particular country where the language is taught, while the second language is a foreign language. Language is taught, while a second language is a language that is not the main language but is one of the languages that is used regularly. One of the languages in general use in a country. While foreign languages is usually taught as one of the subjects in school with the aim of communicating the four language skills (listening, reading, writing, and speaking).

English language literacy is the ability to understand, behave and be literate the importance of English is an international language. Some points that describe that English in elementary school is needed in learning are as follows required in learning are as follows according to Akhyar (2020:1): a) in early childhood learning language is easier to capture b) in today's digital age where all living systems use English, elementary school level children also need to understand English to be used in their daily lives. English to be used in their daily lives, c) understanding English can make a person faster in understanding other foreign languages more quickly too, if elementary school level learners have mastered English and are curious about it. If primary school level learners have mastered English and are curious about other foreign languages, they can learn and master it in a faster period of time, d) besides that, learning English at an early age also has various benefits for children, namely improving cognitive abilities of children realizing the various interests above, then learning English needs to be implemented at the primary school level in Indonesia.

Teaching English is necessary primary school level because learning English has several benefits. Some of these benefits are as follow a) sharpening the child's brain, here the meaning is that if the child learns English then the child will be able to optimize his brain's ability to move in activities in the primary school level. Children will be able to optimize their brain's ability to move in various situations, b) improve the ability to solve problems, this means that children who learn English

will be able to optimize their brain's ability to move in various situations. The children who learn English will be able to solve various problems they face, improve the ability to solve problems, c) improve critical thinking, this means that children are trained to criticize the various findings they find in everyday life d) improve listening skills well because in learning English. English learning there is the ability to listen so this will have an impact on the child's ability to listen well to listen to in everyday life, e) improve memory because in English language learning, children are required to memorize vocabulary, so this will impact on the ability to remember, f) improve the ability to concentrate because of the nature of elementary school children still like to play, the majority of this English learning, g) improve socialization skills because of the universal nature of English. English is universal, of course English is one of the most widely used language in the world community. So if students master English, they can communicate with people from various countries easily (Riziqsiwi et al, 2021; Soeharyono et al, 2022; Larassanti et al, 2022).

Based on the background that has been explained, this research has 2 objectives namely 1) What are the forms of fifth grade English language learning skills at SDN 106161 Medan Estate Deli Serdang Regency, 2) How is the level of difficulty of knowledge of grade V students in learning English at SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Deli Serdang Regency?.

METHODS

The type of research is qualitative research with a descriptive type of research method. This is done so that researchers can describe in detail and get data about the form and level of difficulty in learning English in class V. the research was conducted in May 2024 at SDN 106161 Medan Estate Deli Serdang. Primary data in the form of interview with the principal, English teachers and fifth grade students. Questionnaire to find out the form and level of literacy difficulties experienced by the students. While secondary data is obtained from other relevant supporting sources.

Techniques data collection techniques in the form of observation instruments, interviews, questionnaires, documentation. Source of data are teachers and students. Additional data sources are documents, writings and other important files. According to Sugiono (2019:12), it states that in qualitative research to get valid and reliable data, it must use valid measuring instruments and need to test the validity of the data so that researchers use triangulation techniques by checking data with data sources including the principal and English teachers. The qualitative data analysis method used is the Miles & Huberman method (in Sugiyono, 2019). Stated that activities in research data collection, data reduction, data presentation, data display and conclusion verification. Research refers to Moleong's (2017:127) research stages, namely prefield, fieldwork and data analysis stages.

RESULTS

This research was conducted at SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency. The research subject only a single class, said to be single, namely the researcher only examines one classroom V SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency. Data obtained using observation, interview with the principal, English teacher off class V and learners off class V.

Gambar 1. Profil SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency

Gambar 2. Administering questionnaires to grade V SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency

1) Description of Observation

Results during English learning researchers made observations during fifth grade English language learning which was coincided on Sunday, 6 May 2024 which included observations of the learning process, available infrastructure, elements of learning achievement in accordance with the textbooks used for teaching and learning activities, goals and objectives the forms of implementation of learning English in class V of SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency.

2) Description of research interview results

a) results of interview with principal

researchers to the principal of SDN 106161, namely learning English is a locally-charged subject, there is no extracurricular activity to develop student's talents specifically in the field of English. English lessons are still in the content of the 2013 curriculum which is taught in high grades only starting in grades IV,V,VI. The principal also hopes that students before graduating from Elementary school are able to speak English well and are able to understand vocabulary, grammar and sentence structure. However, the infrastructure for learning English is still incomplete, currently the principal is also still working on the adequacy of facilities and infrastructure that support and produce optimal learning for support and produce optimal learning for students.

b) Results of interview with English Teacher

Based on the interview with the English teacher, the researcher describe as follows: Mrs. Rahmayati's experience of teaching English for 2 years Mrs. Rahma explained that the form of literacy of students already contains 4 namely listening, speaking, writing and reading. Students have difficulties in speaking English, students are still shy and afraid of being wrong in speak English. The purpose of Mrs. Rahma choosing the model is so that students are more able to learn and the advantages of students being able to think critically. The advantage is that students are able to think critically and actively in learning. The approach used in learning English class V is approach or what is called the approach what is called the approach from their own experience so that it has the advantages of learners being more interested because it learning process there must be an evaluation process as well, Mrs. Rahma uses selective evaluation (according to criteria), diagnostic evaluation (healing student's difficulties). The conclusion from the interview with Mrs. Rahma as the English teacher and guardian teacher is that the level of knowledge of teacher, can be said that the students have not mastered the vocabulary of English which includes 4 forms, namely listening, speaking, reading and writing.

c) The results of interviews with fifth grade student of SDN 106161 Medan Estate

it explains that in the second point about listening 20 students have the ability of English lessons in the listening section with a result of 100%. The question of whether listening is their favorite, getting 80% of the answers in the yes category and 20% in the no category. But, students have difficulty in understanding listening lessons with a balance as evidenced by the results of the

questionnaire 50% of the answers in the yes category and 50% of the answers in the no category.

3) Description of research questionnaire results

The results of the questionnaire were obtained by distributing to class V students. Questionnaire filling is done individually. In this study using two alternative answers Yes and No which are accompanied by a description.

Tabel 1. Results of filling out the questionnaire

No.	Description	Yes	No
Listening			
1.	Liked the listening part of English lessons	80 % (14)	20% (6)
2.	Listening is one of the skills learners	100% (20)	-
3	Experiencing difficulties during English lessons listening section	50% (10)	50% (10)
Speaking			
4	Liked speaking part of English lessons	80% (16)	20% (4)
5	Speaking is one of the skills learner's	90% (18)	10% (2)
6	Experiencing difficulties during english lessons speaking section	80% (14)	20% (6)
Writing			
7	Liked the writing part of the English lesson	75% (15)	25% (5)
8	Writing is one of the learners skills	90% (18)	10% (2)
9	Having difficulty during English lessons writing section	50% (10)	50% (10)
Reading			
10	Liked the reading part of the English lesson	75% (15)	25% (5)
11	Reading is one of the student's skills	90% (18)	10% (2)
12	Having difficulty during english lessons reading section	65% (13)	35% (7)

From the questionnaire results above, it explains that in the second point about listening 20 students have the ability of English lessons in the listening section with a result of 100%. The question of whether listening is their favorite, getting 80% of the answers in the yes category and 20% in the yes category. But, students have difficulty in understanding listening lessons with a balance as evidenced by the results of the questionnaire 50% of the answers in the yes category and 50% of the answers in the no category.

DISCUSSION

Based on the research data that has been collected, the next step is the discussion of the research results on the form of literacy skills. The next step is the discussion of the results of research on English language learning and the level of ability of fifth grade students in SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency. Naiborhu Romasta (2019: 7-12) said that English lessons have four aspects of the form of ability English language learning, namely aspect of speaking, listening, reading and writing.

1) forms of literacy skills found in students of SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency.

a) Listening

Based on the results of the research by analyzing the results of observations, interviews, questionnaires and document of the English language learning process there is already a form of listening ability as evidenced by the results of the observation of the document package book which includes listening achievement indicators used for English language learning. With strengthened evidence of observation of the results of English learning shows that students are enthusiastic about learning and able to listen to the material well delivered the teacher using the lecture/direct metode.

b) Speaking

Based on the results of the research by analyzing the results of observations, interviews,

questionnaires and document of the English language learning process there is already a form of speaking ability as evidenced by the results of the observation of the document package book which includes listening achievement indicators used for English language learning. With strengthened evidence of observation of the results of English learning results students are trained to speak directly when asking questions using simple vocabulary.

c) Writing

Based on research when researchers observed teaching and learning activities in the fifth grade SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency that language learning already has a form of writing ability as evidenced by the support of a package book and also indicators and also when learning students are assisted by the teacher with whiteboard facilities to write answers to English questions given by the teacher.

d) Reading

learning activities can not be separated from reading activities, based on the results of the research of fifth grade SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency.

There is a form of reading ability as evidenced by the support of the package books that contain indicators and students at the beginning of learning are asked to read the learning material in their respective package books. It can be concluded that the form of literacy skills in English language learning in grade V SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency, there are four forms of literacy skills namely: 1) listening there is a listening process in English learning, 2) speaking there is a process in English speaking, 3) reading there is a reading process in English reading, 4) writing there is a process in English writing.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted on the analysis of literacy in English language learning in grade V SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency can be concluded as follows:

1. forms of literacy skills in fifth grade SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency, namely there are four aspects of listening, reading, writing and speaking.
2. The level of difficulty English language learning on fifth grade SDN 106161 Medan Estate, Percut Sei Tuan Sub-district, Deli Serdang Regency, namely having difficulty in the speaking section and the use of vocabulary that is not well understood. Vocabulary that is still considered difficult for students so that it results in speaking. Which is upside down between the meaning and the way it is pronounced.

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